

NOTES

Nickel(II) Complexes with Substituted Amino Benzothiazoles

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Manuscript received 7 August 1981, accepted 1 May 1982

In our recent work^{1,2} we reported the synthesis of a series of Co(II), Cu(II) and Hg(II) complexes with substituted amino benzothiazoles. As an extension of the previous studies, the present communication describes the preparation and characterisation of some Ni(II) complexes with the monodentate ligands, 2-amino-6-methyl benzothiazole and 2-amino-6-chloro benzothiazole.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The substituted amino benzothiazoles have been synthesised by standard procedure³.

Preparation of the complexes: Methanolic solution of the nickel(II) salts were reacted separately with methanolic solution of the substituted amino benzothiazoles in 1 : 2 ratio and refluxed for about 2 hr. Crystalline compounds separated out on cooling. These were filtered, washed with methanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Metal contents of the complexes were estimated gravimetrically as dimethyl glyoximate. Nitrogen and sulphur were estimated by standard procedure. Conductance was measured in 10⁻³ M acetone solution using Toshniwal conductivity bridge. IR

spectra were recorded in KBr phase using Unicam Sp-1025 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra of the complexes in chloroform solution were recorded by using Hilger Watt Uvispeck spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

All the eight complexes reported in the present investigation are of the composition [Ni(L₂ or L'₂)X₂] and [Ni(L₂ or L'₂)]Y₂, where X = Cl⁻, NO₂⁻, SCN⁻ and Y = ClO₄⁻; L = 2-amino-6-methyl benzothiazole and L' = 2-amino-6-chloro benzothiazole. All the complexes of the composition [Ni(L₂ or L'₂)X₂] are yellow to deep brown in colour whereas the two perchlorate complexes are green in colour. The complexes have low melting points and are soluble in acetone in which medium they are found to be non-electrolytes, the Δ_M being in the range of 10-25 mhos cm² except for the perchlorate complexes. The Δ_M values of the two perchlorate complexes are found to be around 230 mhos cm² indicating 1 : 2 electrolytic nature of these complexes.

The ir spectra show a sharp peak at ~815 cm⁻¹ in the free ligands which can be assigned¹ to $\nu(C-S)$ vibrations. On complexation, this frequency is shifted down to lower frequency region of ~800 cm⁻¹ indicating the bonding of the benzothiazole molecule to metal ions through ring sulphur atom. The bands observed⁴ around 1535 and ~3250 cm⁻¹ in the free ligands are due to $\nu(C=N)$ and $\nu(N-H)$ vibrations, respectively. No change of these bands has been noticed in the complexes which conclusively proves that both the

TABLE I—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND IR SPECTRAL DATA

Compound	%Metal Found (Calcd.)	%N Found (Calcd.)	%S Found (Calcd.)	Δ_M mhos cm ²	μ_{eff} B.M.	$\nu(C-S)$
[NiL ₂ Cl ₂]	12.74 (12.89)	12.08 (12.28)	13.82 (13.98)	10.8	—	805
[NiL' ₂ Cl ₂]	11.60 (11.77)	11.12 (11.28)	12.70 (12.88)	11.6	—	795
[NiL ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]	11.41 (11.49)	16.34 (16.44)	12.40 (12.58)	16.5	—	800
[NiL' ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]	10.52 (10.64)	15.10 (15.22)	11.42 (11.60)	18.0	—	800
[NiL ₂ (SCN) ₂]	11.58 (11.67)	16.59 (16.71)	25.34 (25.46)	22.4	—	810
[NiL' ₂ (SCN) ₂]	10.66 (10.80)	15.36 (15.45)	23.40 (23.54)	20.8	—	805
[NiL ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	6.90 (6.42)	12.16 (12.26)	13.92 (14.01)	225.0	3.80	800
[NiL' ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	5.72 (5.89)	11.12 (11.25)	12.72 (12.85)	228.0	3.60	795

L = 2-amino-6-methyl benzothiazole.
L' = 2-amino-6-chloro benzothiazole.

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endo- and exo-cyclic nitrogen atoms are not bonded to the metal ions. In the nitrate complexes, absorption bands appear in the region ~ 1280 and 1400 cm^{-1} . The position of ν_4 and ν_1 and their separation ($\Delta\nu$) of $\sim 120\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggest⁵⁻⁷ the nitrate group to be monodentate in the two complexes. The thiocyanato complexes have two sharp bands at ~ 2080 and 735 cm^{-1} attributable^{8,9} to $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ vibrations, respectively of N-bonded terminal thiocyanato group. In the present investigation, an increase of $30-40\text{ cm}^{-1}$ relative to the free thiocyanate ion is indicative of N-bonded terminal thiocyanate group on the basis of previous observations¹⁰. The appearance of a broad hump in the region $1040-1150\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates¹¹⁻¹³ the presence of ionic perchlorate group in the two perchlorate complexes and this is also corroborated by the molar conductance data of these complexes.

The chloro-, nitrate- and thiocyanato complexes are found to be diamagnetic. The perchlorate complexes have high magnetic moments (3.6 to 3.8 B. M.) indicating¹⁴ a tetrahedral environment.

Visible electronic spectra of the chloro-, nitrate- and thiocyanato nickel(II) complexes show absorption bands at ~ 19800 and 20000 cm^{-1} and have relatively high extinction coefficient values, indicative of a square configuration. In case of the perchlorate complexes, two bands are observed at $\sim 15200(180)$ and $8100(35)\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributable to ${}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})\rightarrow{}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ and ${}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})\rightarrow{}^3\text{A}_{2g}$ transitions, respectively. The high molar absorptivity values of the former band and the high magnetic moment values suggest¹⁵ a possible tetrahedral geometry for the two complexes.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (R. P. M.) is indebted to Dr. D. C. Pati, Department of Chemistry, B. J. B. College, Bhubaneswar for help.

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Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) with Chelating Bidentate Schiff's Base

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Manuscript received 22 May 1981, revised 2 December 1981,
accepted 23 May 1982

WE have been trying to synthesise complexes of rare coordination number through complexation of polydentate ligands with divalent metal salts. Earlier, we reported¹⁻³ metal complexes with bi-, tri- and tetradentate ligands having oxygen-nitrogen oxygen-sulphur, nitrogen-sulphur and oxygen-nitrogen-sulphur as the potential bonding sites. The present communication describes the synthesis and characterisation of six metal complexes with a new bidentate Schiff's base derived from benzoin and aniline.

Experimental

All the chemicals were analytical reagent grade products.

Preparation of the Schiff's base : To a methanolic solution of benzoin (2.12 g) and aniline (1.0 ml) was added anhydrous sodium acetate (4.0 g) and the mixture was refluxed for 1 hr over a water bath. The hot solution was poured into ice-cold water when a yellowish crystalline precipitate of the Schiff's base separated out. It was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from rectified spirit, m. p. 130° , yield 60%. (Found : C, 82.64; H, 5.52; N, 4.84. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{ON}$ requires C, 83.91; H, 5.59; N, 4.89%).

Preparation of the complexes : Ethanolic solutions of the metallic chlorides were treated separately with ethanolic solution of the Schiff's base in 1 : 2 molar ratio followed by drop-wise addition of ammonia when metallic chelates separated out. These were filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Metal content of the complexes was estimated by complexometric EDTA titration method. The conductance measurements were carried out with a Toshniwal conductivity bridge in $1 \times 10^{-3}\text{ M}$ acetone solution of the complexes. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at room temperature using Gouy method. Electronic spectra were recorded in $1 \times 10^{-3}\text{ M}$ chloroform solution of the complexes using Hilger Watt Uvispeck spectrophotometer. The infrared spectra on Nujol mulls